

**The Neuroprotective Role of Passive Music Therapy in Alzheimer's Disease: Effects on
Cortisol Regulation and Stress Reduction**

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There are no changes in affiliation to disclose.

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Abstract

Alzheimer's disease, also known as AD, is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder and is one of the most prominent causes of dementia. Symptoms include memory loss, cognitive decline, and neuronal death. Current pharmacological treatments provide limited relief and do not address the underlying neurodegenerative processes, prompting the need for complementary and non-invasive treatments. Music therapy has been recognised as a potential supportive treatment, with research suggesting it enhances mood and memory. However, its biological influence, especially its effect on cortisol, a core stress hormone implicated in neurodegeneration, remains underexplored. This research proposal aims to investigate the role of passive music therapy can modulate cortisol levels and reduce stress-related neurotoxicity in patients with Alzheimer's disease. By combining biological measures of cortisol with standardised psychological assessments, this paper seeks to determine whether music therapy can provide both emotional and neuroprotective benefits. The expected outcome is a clearer understanding how passive music therapy may serve as a low-cost, non-invasive option in contrast to traditional pharmacological treatments, promoting emotional stability and reducing stress-induced neural damage.

Based on previous research linking chronic stress and elevated cortisol to hippocampal atrophy and accelerated cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease, it is expected that passive music therapy may lead to reduced physiological stress and improved psychological outcomes. Our study follows a systematic approach in which participants undergo a controlled passive music listening condition and a quiet rest control condition, with salivary cortisol levels and standardised psychological measures assessed before and after each session. This integrated

biological and psychological approach aims to clarify whether passive music therapy provides both emotional and neuroprotective benefits as a low-cost, non-invasive adjunct to conventional Alzheimer's disease care.

Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is one of the most prominent neurodegenerative disorders globally, impacting over 55 million people and is a rising public health concern[1][2]. Characterised by memory loss, cognitive decline and behavioural changes, AD gradually leads to neuronal death, especially in the hippocampus and cerebral cortex[3][4]. Current pharmacological treatments such as acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (AChEIs) and N-methyl-d-aspartate (NMDA) receptor antagonist memantine, primarily target the symptoms of AD but fail to prevent or reverse neurodegeneration[5][6]. This limitation emphasises the need for non-pharmacological interventions that support both emotional and biological stability.

Music therapy, the clinical use of music to achieve therapeutic goals has shown potential in improving AD patients emotional well-being, cognitive function and quality of life[7][8][9]. Passive music therapy, involves listening to pre-selected or personally meaningful music, can evoke positive emotions, stimulate memory recall and reduce anxiety[7][10]. Emerging research suggests that music therapy may have positive biological effects, such as reducing the levels of cortisol, the body's core stress hormone[10][11][12]. High cortisol levels are associated with hippocampal atrophy and accelerated cognitive decline in AD, making stress regulation a key factor in disease management[11][12][13].

Despite the growing evidence connecting music therapy to improved mental health, the neuroendocrine pathways where music may exert protective effects remains poorly understood. This research proposal aims to fill this gap by analysing whether passive music therapy can

reduce cortisol levels and also lower stress related neurotoxicity . The study will follow a simple experimental approach in which salivary cortisol measurements are taken immediately before and after a controlled passive music listening session and compared to a quiet rest control condition.

Based on previous studies and our understanding, passive music therapy will greatly reduce cortisol levels in patients with AD, therefore indicating activation of beneficial neuroendocrine pathways. The expected outcome is evidence supporting passive music therapy as a biologically grounded, non-pharmological accessible intervention capable of emotional stability and neuroprotection in people living with Alzheimer's disease.

Literature Review

Current Understanding of Alzheimer's Disease

Alzheimer's disease(AD) is characterised by continuous neurodegeneration associated with β -amyloid accumulation, tau protein tangles, synaptic dysfunction and widespread neuronal loss [3][4]. Neurodegeneration is mainly found in the hippocampus and cortical regions responsible for memory, learning and emotional regulation. This biological deterioration emphasises the clinical symptoms of cognitive decline, behavioural changes and impaired daily function[1][2]

The Role of Stress and Cortisol in Neurodegeneration

Chronic stress and dysregulation of the hypothalamic pituitary adrenal (HPA) axis is increasingly being recognised as a key contributing factor in neurodegenerative disease. Elevated cortisol

levels have been shown to quicken hippocampal atrophy, reduce synaptic plasticity and impair cognitive functions essential for memory formation[11][12]. Individuals with consistent high cortisol may have increased risk of both cognitive decline and development of dementia[11][12][13].

Knezevic et al. (2023) demonstrated that chronic cortisol elevation contributes to oxidative stress, neuroinflammation and neuronal apoptosis, mechanisms central to Alzheimer's disease and other neurodegenerative disorders[15] . This further strengthens the arguments that stress biology places a face to face role in accelerating neurodegeneration and supports the needs that target cortisol regulation.

Despite the strong evidence linking cortisol to neuronal damage, no current pharmacological treatments effectively reduce cortisol in AD patients revealing a huge therapeutic gap.

Biological & Neuroendocrine Effects of Music

Beyond psychological effects, music also influences physiological systems. Studies show that listening to calming or preferred music can reduce heart rate, modulate the autonomic nervous system, and decrease markers of sympathetic arousal [10].

However, music may affect the hypothalamic pituitary adrenal (HPA) axis, the body's primary stress response system [11]. Chronic stress and elevated cortisol levels contribute to hippocampal atrophy, impaired synaptic plasticity and faster disease progression in AD. [14][15]. Cortisol dysregulation is therefore a key biological target for AD interventions.

Existing hormonal studies: evidence but limited scope

Some research studies have examined the biological effects of music in AD. The study by Fukui et al. (2012) demonstrated that music therapy increased 17β -estradiol and testosterone levels in Alzheimer's patients, suggesting music can directly alter endocrine activity. This is essential as it shows that biological pathways are influenced by music not only psychological factors.

However these studies largely focus on sex hormones rather than stress hormones like cortisol. Most are short term, involve small samples size or examine biomarkers not related to neurotoxicity. [12][13]

Additionally, although biological effects are under-studied some research studies do investigate hormonal changes in AD during music exposure, meaning the field is not entirely unexplored but remains extremely unlimited in terms of cortisol related mechanisms.

Research Gaps & Limitations in Existing Literature

Although music therapy has shown psychological and cognitive benefits for patients with AD, a major gap remains in the understanding and processes of its biological mechanisms, specifically its effect on cortisol regulation. Most existing studies focus on mood, behaviour or general well being while glossing over specific neuroendocrine pathways. For instance, Fukui et al. (2012) examined hormonal changes but focused on sex hormones rather than cortisol, greatly limiting the biological insight into stress related mechanisms[16]. Other studies assessing

psychological factors have small sample sizes, short study durations or biomarker completely unrelated to neurotoxicity[12][13].

However, strong research studies link cortisol dysregulation to hippocampal atrophy, inflammation, reduced synaptic plasticity and quicker progression of AD, making it an essential biological target[11][14].

Even so, no studies currently evaluate how music therapy affects cortisol specifically in AD patients leaving a huge gap in our understanding in whether passive music listening can reduce stress related neurotoxicity. This proposal directly addresses this gap by using cortisol as a measurable, biological outcome.

Public Perspectives & Skepticism Towards Music Therapy

Despite being supported by emerging research, music therapy is often met with public and clinical skepticism. Some argue it is merely recreational or that its benefits are temporary and personal. Concerns are also rising from inconsistent protocols across studies for instance differences in music type, tempo and duration complicating public confidence in its therapeutic value. Because AD treatment is often dominated by pharmacological treatments such as AChEIs and memantine[5][6].

Caregivers and family perspectives add another important side to this skepticism. While many carers report observing short-term improvements in mood, communication and agitation when music is used, some remain uncertain about its long term clinical value due to inconsistent guidance and lack of clear biological evidence. This uncertainty can influence whether families advocate for music therapy in care plans.

By linking music therapy to quantifiable biological outcomes, specifically cortisol regulation, this research will help counter skepticism and support music therapy as an authentic, evidence based intervention.

Ethics Consideration

This study will obey ethical guidelines for human research. Informed consent will be obtained from participants or their legal guardians, ensuring they thoroughly understand the study's purpose, procedures and minimal risks. Passive music listening is non-invasive and holds minimal discomfort, while salivary cortisol collection is safe and has a low risk. All participant data will be anonymous and stored securely in encrypted research files accessible only to authorised personnel. Approval from a Human Research Ethic Committee (HREC) will be obtained before commencing the study. Participants may withdraw at any time with a reasonable reason without penalty. Participants will be monitored throughout sessions, and testing will be discontinued immediately if distress is observed or reported

Research Question

Does passive music therapy reduce cortisol levels and stress-related neurotoxicity in individuals with Alzheimer's disease?

Method

Study Design

This study will use a randomised, within subjects crossover design to compare the effects of passive music therapy with a quiet rest control condition. [7][8][10]

Primary outcome: change in salivary cortisol concentration (pre-session vs post-session; music condition vs control condition). [10][11][15]

Secondary outcomes: changes in mood and agitation, measured using standardised psychological scales. [7][8][15]

Participants will complete both conditions in a counterbalanced order. Randomisation of condition order will be conducted using a computer-generated random sequence (block randomisation with blocks of four) prepared by an independent researcher not involved in data collection. A washout period of 24–48 hours between sessions will be implemented to minimise carryover effects, which is appropriate given the acute, short-term physiological effects of music on stress biomarkers.[10][11]

A crossover design is suitable for this study because cortisol levels and psychological states vary substantially between individuals with AD. By allowing each participant to act as their

own control, inter-individual variability is reduced and statistical power is improved, which is particularly important in a feasibility-based sample.[6][7]

All sessions will be conducted within a standardised morning time window (9:00–11:00 am) to minimise circadian variation in cortisol secretion[11][14]. Environmental conditions (lighting, room temperature, seating, and ambient noise) will be held constant across sessions.

Participants

Participants will be adults aged 65 years and older with a clinically confirmed diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease according to National Institute on Aging criteria. Recruitment will occur through memory clinics and aged care facilities. Clinicians at these sites will inform eligible patients and caregivers about the study, and recruitment materials (flyers and posters) will also be displayed in waiting areas. Caregivers may initiate contact with the research team on behalf of potential participants.

Exclusion criteria will include:

- Severe or end-stage Alzheimer's disease where participants are unable to comply with procedures
- Significant hearing impairment that prevents participation in music listening
- Current major psychiatric disorders (e.g. major depressive disorder with psychotic features)
- Use of systemic corticosteroid medication
- Acute medical illness at the time of testing

Capacity to provide informed consent will be assessed by a trained clinician. Where participants lack full decision-making capacity, written consent will be obtained from a legally authorised representative, and participant assent will be sought wherever possible. Participants may withdraw at any time without penalty, particularly if they experience distress or discomfort.

A target sample size of 25–30 participants is proposed based on feasibility, anticipated recruitment rates, and consistency with prior music therapy studies in dementia populations. While not powered to detect small effects, this sample size is sufficient to estimate effect sizes and assess protocol feasibility.

Participants will receive a small reimbursement (e.g. gift voucher) to compensate for time and travel.

Procedure

After consent and assent procedures are completed, participants will attend two testing sessions (music and control). At the beginning of each session, a baseline saliva sample will be collected using sterile Salivette® swabs.

Music condition: Participants will listen to calming music for 30 minutes. Music will be selected using a semi-personalised approach: participants or caregivers will nominate preferred calming music from a predefined list of genres (e.g. classical, instrumental, slow-tempo contemporary). Calming music will be defined as music with a slow tempo (approximately 60–80 bpm), minimal lyrical complexity, and low rhythmic variability. Playback will occur via

over-ear headphones using the same audio device for all participants, with volume standardised to approximately 60–65 dB.

Control condition: Participants will sit quietly for 30 minutes in the same room and seating arrangement, without auditory stimulation. Participants will be seated upright in a comfortable chair and may close their eyes but will be instructed not to engage in deliberate meditation or relaxation techniques.

Immediately following each session, a second saliva sample will be collected. Psychological measures of mood and agitation will then be administered by a trained researcher. All samples will be frozen at -20°C until biochemical analysis.

To reduce bias, laboratory technicians analysing cortisol samples and data analysts conducting statistical analyses will be blinded to condition and time point (pre vs post).

Participants will be monitored throughout sessions, and testing will be discontinued immediately if distress is observed or reported.

Psychological Measures

Mood will be assessed using the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS), and agitation will be measured using the Cohen–Mansfield Agitation Inventory (CMAI) both of which are widely used and validated in dementia research [7][15]. These measures will be administered immediately after each session and require approximately 10–15 minutes to complete. Assessments will be conducted by trained researchers familiar with dementia-sensitive assessment protocols. PANAS was selected for its sensitivity to short-term changes in affect following brief interventions, while CMAI is considered a gold-standard

measure for detecting changes in agitation-related behaviours in individuals with Alzheimer's disease. These measures will be administered immediately after each session and require approximately **10–15 minutes** to complete. Assessments will be conducted by trained researchers familiar with dementia-sensitive assessment protocols.

Data Analysis

Salivary cortisol concentrations will be analysed using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Statistical analyses will be conducted using SPSS (version XX) or R.

Primary analyses will involve repeated-measures ANOVA comparing cortisol changes across condition (music vs control) and time (pre vs post). Assumptions of normality and sphericity will be assessed; cortisol values will be log-transformed if distributions are non-normal.

Missing or unusable cortisol samples will be handled using pairwise deletion, with sensitivity analyses conducted where appropriate.

Secondary analyses will examine changes in mood and agitation scores using repeated-measures ANOVA, with Bonferroni corrections applied for multiple comparisons. Pearson or Spearman correlations will assess relationships between cortisol changes and psychological outcomes.

Effect sizes (Cohen's d or partial η^2) and 95% confidence intervals will be reported. Data visualisation will include boxplots, line graphs of pre–post changes, and scatterplots illustrating cortisol–psychological relationships.

Given the feasibility-based sample size, analyses will focus on estimating effect sizes rather than definitive hypothesis testing.

Expected Outcomes

It is expected that passive music therapy will result in a moderate reduction in salivary cortisol levels relative to the quiet rest control condition, with anticipated effect sizes in the small-to-moderate range (Cohen's $d \approx 0.4-0.6$). Improvements in mood and reductions in agitation are also expected following the music condition compared with control.

These effects are anticipated to occur immediately following the music session, reflecting acute stress reduction. However, variability is expected due to individual differences in disease severity, music preference, and baseline stress levels. Improvements are expected relative to the control condition, rather than as absolute changes.

Given the modest sample size and short-term design, conclusions regarding long-term neuroprotective effects will be limited.

Feasibility & Limitations

This study is highly feasible due to contributing factors such as non-invasive processes, low cost and minimal participant burden. Passive music listening requires no specialised equipment beyond audio playback devices and salivary cortisol sampling is safe, quick and well tolerated by individuals with mild to moderate Alzheimer's disease. The within subjects design further enhances the feasibility by reducing the required sample size while at the same time increasing statistical power, as each participant is their own control. Recruitment through

memory clinics and aged care facilities is practical and many institutions also support music based activities, making integration of the intervention into daily routine smooth.

However, several limitations must and have been acknowledged. Firstly, variability in individual music preferences may influence therapeutic outcomes, making it challenging to standardise the intervention across participants. Secondly, cortisol levels naturally change throughout the day and although testing will be time controlled, residual variation may still occur. Thirdly, the short term nature of the study limits the ability to assess long-term neuroprotective effects and outcomes will primarily reflect acute rather than sustained responses. Furthermore, individuals with more advanced cognitive impairment may have difficulty following procedures for instance providing saliva samples or remaining still during a listening session. Finally, as the sample will likely be modest due to feasibility constraint the generalisation of findings to the broader AD population may be limited.

Despite these limitations, the study remains practical and capable of generating evidence regarding the biological and emotional impact of passive music therapy in Alzheimer's disease.

Future Scope

Future research could build on top of this study by exploring longer intervention periods and large, more diverse participant samples to strengthen validity. While current research has shown benefits for mood, memory and behavioral symptoms [7][10][15], very few studies have assessed whether repeated cortisol reduction can contribute to slower hippocampal atrophy or reduced neurodegeneration over time, despite high cortisol being linked to accelerated neuronal

loss [13][14]. Longer intervention period (e.g. several months) may further clarify whether music therapy can produce sustained neuroprotective outcomes, rather than short-term stress relief.

Further studies could also explore neuroimaging methods such as functional MRI or structural MRI, to directly measure change in brain regions affected by AD (e.g. hippocampus, prefrontal cortex) [3][4]. In addition, future research could compare the different types of music (e.g. personalised playlists vs calming classical music) in order to determine whether the emotional relevance of music enhances cortisol reduction or psychological responses [10][15]. There is also potential for expanding the research to caregiver delivered intervention, allowing families to administer music therapy at home, an approach that may reduce caregiver burden and improve quality of life for both patients and families [15].

Conclusion

This research proposal addresses a huge gap in the current literature by examining whether passive music therapy can modulate cortisol levels, a biological marker closely tied to stress related neurodegeneration [13][14] in individuals with Alzheimer's disease. While past studies have demonstrated improvements in emotional well-being, memory and behavioral symptoms through music therapy [7][8][15], few have connected these psychological benefits to measure biological outcomes. By using a control within subjects design, collecting salivary cortisol samples and assessing emotional measure before and after intervention, this study aims

to provide evidence for both the emotional and neurobiological benefits of passive music listening.

We anticipate that music therapy will lead to reduced cortisol levels, improved mood and agitation, and a positive relationship between stress reduction and emotional well-being. If these expectations are supported, the findings will strengthen the case for music therapy as a low-cost, accessible, non-invasive supplement to conventional AD treatment, addressing public skepticism by grounding therapeutic claims in biological evidence. While limitations such as short intervention duration and limited sample size must be acknowledged, this study provides an important foundation for future longitudinal and neuroimaging research. Future directions include extended interventions, caregiver-delivered protocols, and examination of sustained biological and clinical outcomes.

Overall, this study has potential to contribute meaningful preliminary data, guide future neuroimaging research and support the integration of music therapy into mainstream Alzheimer's care.

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